

References

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Spectrophotometric Studies of Iron(III) complexes with Carboxylic acids using an Auxiliary Complexing Agent

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SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC studies on complex formation between iron(III) and 2-hydroxybutyrophene (OHB) and 2-hydroxy-4-methylbutyrophene (4MeOHB) have been reported by us earlier^{1,2}. We report now the use of these phenones as an auxiliary ligand in determining the composition of the colourless complexes formed by citric, oxalic, malonic and ethylene diamine tetraacetic acids with iron(III) in acid media.

Experimental

OHB and 4MeOHB were prepared as described earlier^{1,2}. Standard reagent solutions were prepared by dissolving weighed amounts of reagent in pure methanol. All other chemicals used were of A.R. quality. The stock iron(III) solutions was prepared as shown earlier³. The stock solutions of citric acid, oxalic acid, malonic acid and ethylenediamine tetraacetic acid were prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of each in 0.01M HNO₃. Dilute solutions of same acidity but desired concentrations were obtained as and when needed by diluting the stock solution with 0.01M HNO₃. All aqueous solutions were prepared in water twice distilled over alkaline permanganate.

Spectrophotometric measurements were made on Zeiss-Specol, using 1 cm matched cells. All measurements were carried out at 30° ± 1° in a 50% water—50% methanol (by volume) medium adjusted to 0.005M with respect to nitric acid.

The method used has been described earlier³. A solution containing FeA⁺² (5 × 10⁻⁴M) was prepared by mixing equal volumes of iron(III) (1 × 10⁻³M) and A (1 × 10⁻²M) (A = OHB or 4MeOHB) solutions. The continuous variation⁴ studies were carried out using 5 × 10⁻⁴M FeA⁺² and 5 × 10⁻⁴M carboxylic acid solutions. The absorbances were measured at 530 nm since this is the λ_{max} for both Fe(III)-OHB and Fe(III)-4MeOHB systems^{1,2}.

Two sets of solutions for each equilibrium, one with and the other without the carboxylic acid were prepared. The difference in the absorbances of the pair of corresponding solutions for the two sets corresponds to the Y function in Job's curve. Maximum in Y indicates 1:1 composition for the colourless complexes of iron(III) with citric acid, oxalic acid, malonic acid and EDTA. Typical results are shown in Fig. 1. for Fe(III)-OHB-EDTA system. It can be seen from Fig. 1 that the maximum

Fig. 1. Job's curves in equimolar solutions for the iron(III)-OHB-EDTA system.
Curve A: Fe(III)-OHB
Curve B: Fe(III)-OHB-EDTA
Curve C: Difference of curves A and B.

decolourisation was observed at a ratio of iron(III): EDTA = 1:1. This indicates the formation of a complex correspondingly used. Results obtained with citric acid, oxalic and malonic acids also indicated that iron(III) formed 1:1 complexes with these acids under the conditions of the present study.

In order to find out if mixed ligand complex formation occurred under the conditions of study, the following test was done for each equilibrium studied. To a solution containing iron(III) and excess A, increasing amounts of carboxylic acid were added and the absorbance was measured. The absorbance over the entire visible range was observed to decrease as the concentration of the added carboxylic acid increased. This was interpreted to indicate a progressive conversion of FeA⁺² to Fe-carboxylate complex. It was concluded therefore that no mixed ligand complexes were formed, atleast under the conditions of present study, in these systems.

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**Action of Dinitrogen tetroxide and its Thermal
Dissociation Products on Anhydrous Neutral
Alkali Salts of Tetrachlorophthallic Acid**

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THE present work is in continuation of the work done by one of the authors (V.T.O.)¹ and is now extended to study the action of dinitrogen tetroxide and its thermal dissociation products on neutral anhydrous sodium, potassium and lithium tetrachlorophthalate. It is interesting to observe that lithium salt behaves in slightly different manner than the sodium and potassium salts; especially in its behaviour with nitrogen dioxide above room temperature

The reaction of nitrogen gases on neutral sodium salts of some organic monobasic and dibasic acids have been investigated in past by Rodinov and Obliteva² and reviewed by Riebsomer and Reineke³. Further work was published by one of the authors (V T O)¹

Experimental

Neutral salts of the tetrachlorophth acid were prepared by the method suggested in the literature⁴. Their purity was established by determining the weight of sulphates formed by the treatment with conc H₂SO₄. The preparation of dinitrogen tetroxide and the experimental technique were the same as described by Oza⁵. The residue was first extracted with suitable organic solvent to remove organic compounds formed. It was later treated with water to dissolve inorganic compounds formed. Nonaqueous extracts after evaporating to dryness were analysed by standard methods. It showed presence of the anhydride. The qualitative analysis of the water extract showed the presence of nitrate ions together with the unreacted salt. The quantitative determination of nitrate was done by standard method⁶.

Results and Discussion

Results of the experiments indicate that sodium and potassium salts react completely with dinitrogen tetroxide and the reaction may be formulated as under. The lithium salt, however, behaves in a slightly different manner. The ionic species⁷ present

TABLE—TETRACHLOROPHTHALATE—LIQUID DINITROGEN TETROXIDE SYSTEM

Expt. No.	Substance taken	Liquid N ₂ O ₄ taken	Nitrate formed	Anhydride formed	N ₂ O ₄ used up	N ₂ O ₃ formed
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
(a) System Na-Chlorophthalat + Liquid N ₂ O ₄						
1.	0.0502 (1.40)	0.2445 (26.6)	0.02455 (2.88)	0.0413 (1.44)	0.0272 (3.00)	0.01095 (1.44)
2.	0.0750 (2.15)	0.2875 (31.20)	0.0368 (4.30)	0.0615 (2.15)	0.0397 (4.30)	0.0165 (2.17)
(b) System K-Chlorophthalat + Liquid N ₂ O ₄						
3.	0.0500 (1.31)	0.2155 (23.24)	0.0266 (2.60)	0.0375 (1.31)	0.0242 (2.60)	0.0100 (1.32)
4.	0.0825 (2.17)	0.2754 (29.90)	0.0440 (4.30)	0.0623 (2.18)	0.0400 (4.30)	0.0165 (2.18)
(c) System Li-Chlorophthalate + Liquid N ₂ O ₄						
5.	0.0500 (1.60)	0.2155 (23.4)	0.0161 (2.3)	0.0334 (1.17)	0.0216 (2.30)	0.0089 (1.17)
6.	0.0701 (2.20)	0.2369 (25.8)	0.0212 (3.00)	0.0438 (1.53)	0.0284 (3.10)	0.0117 (1.54)
7.	0.0510 (1.62)	0.2059 (22.4)	0.0218 (3.15)	0.0454 (1.61)	0.0292 (3.20)	0.0120 (1.58)
8.	0.072 (2.28)	0.2100 (22.8)	0.0285 (4.10)	0.0592 (2.08)	0.0385 (4.20)	0.0158 (2.08)

Figures in () indicate gram molecules (multiplied by 10⁻⁴)

Expts No. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, were conducted at 0°C

Expts No. 1 to 4 were conducted for 1/2 hr. and 100% reaction took place.

Expts No. 5 and 6 were conducted for 24 hrs.

Expts No. 7 and 8 were conducted for 1 hr.